

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17548255

Investigation into Funding of Tertiary Institutions own by Sokoto State under Distressed Economy

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ABSTRACT

This study examined funding of Nigeria's tertiary institutions for effective teaching and learning towards sustainable educational development. It was observed that current and past predicaments of higher education in Nigeria are inextricably linked to insufficient funding as a vital sector for sustainable development in Nigeria's educational system. For the past five decades tertiary education has depended on inadequate government budgetary appropriations and inadequacy of school fees. Nigerian universities function with the shortage in key educational resources, such as research materials, library facilities, science lab equipment, and suffer the consequences of under-funding from students. The study would examine the relationship between developments of Nigeria's tertiary institution vis-a-vis funding of higher education. Three study objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses were raised for the study. The sample for the study composed of 300 participants taken from tertiary institutions in sokoto-state as research subjects for gathering data. The data elicited were subjected to tests of normality measures of central tendency and subsequently tested for correlational relationship by regression analysis which indicated the degree of association between sustainable development of sokoto state's higher institutions adequacy of funding of higher education for effective teaching and learning on the other. The study results provided a plat-form for scrutinizing application of funds to justify the paucity of sources of funding and worthiness of additional funding from alternative sources. It showed that scrutiny of financial reforms provided unearh loopholes and leakages in the spreading stream of tertiary institutions that brought a bases for openness in financial administration to be able to source alternative funds in order to restore the past glory of higher education, particularly in the area of research and quality learning which were the hallmarks of the technological knowledge driven for availability and accessibility of TET Fund financial assistance for improvement of infrastructure, provision of equipment and for manpower training and development. it was imperative for higher educational institutions to justify their inclusion by meeting their mandate of quality teaching and conducting cutting research through available resources

Keywords: funding of tertiary institutions, distressed economy

INTRODUCTION

Issues arising from inadequate funding of education in general and higher education in particular are too numerous to or contemplate. Nigeria's higher educational system has experienced a major degradation in

the past five decades. This phenomenon has been deleterious to education because most colleges and universities have declined from their lofty positions to low-level today (Enzewo, 2014:15). When viewed from inception when these institutions began to open their doors to students, they were adjudged to be at par with those in developed countries in terms of funding (Ajani, 2007).

The structural adjustment programme (SAP) of the mid-1980s changed the face of higher education in Nigeria as universities and colleges literally collapsed. Physical and other infrastructural features began to deteriorate. Libraries, Laboratories, lecture halls, halls of residence and other facilities that are critical and necessary to pursue academic and scholarly excellence became neglected, dilapidated and barely functional features began to flee to the country in search of greener pastures, leaving behind those who did not have the financial muscle to go or just refused to abandon the country for reasons of patriotism (Andrew, 2011).

The foregoing has had impact on the staffing position in many tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Today delimitating departmental staffing of low-caliber lecturers with most of them receiving from their degrees locally unlike in the past when most faculties and departments were cosmopolitan. In the past most lecturers received their degrees from many top universities around the world. The implication is that the bulk of these teachers in almost all colleges and universities are now local rather than cosmopolitan. To put it in the words of Akinniyi (2010), “they are all homegrown”.

No government or tertiary institution can provide all the funds needed by higher education to pursue research, teaching and other critical components of the higher education system. At best governments and financial institutions inadequate amounts of money from their annual budgetary appropriations for activities of higher education indeed, universities, colleges, research institutions and similar such tertiary entities expect their staff to source for funds from external bodies for their research and other academic pursuits (Ifeanyi, 2017). This means the faculty even in top rated universities and colleges in advanced nations depends on external grants to augment their salaries or cover their salaries and/ or train their graduate students.

Nigeria’s higher education seems to be lagging behind other nations ‘in advancement in science and technology (Anyah,2013). This might be due to lack of capacity for research or has not been given a priority in policy measures affecting research output and higher education in general (Adegbite,2007). Research capacity implies the aggregate of human .institutional and financial conditions for pursuing advancement in knowledge. Funding is therefore would be a critical in building capacity for research and ancillary activities like institutions. If funds are available, where other institutional capacity factors like human resources do not exist, higher education could still be restored to its past glory. Therefore, as it is currently, Nigeria’s higher institutions of learning are predisposed to sourcing for additional funds elsewhere, locally or globally without government endorsement. Regrettably, Nigerian governments since independence have not been making subtending allocation of funds to education in general and higher education in particular as per 26 percent of the nation’s budgetary appropriation required by the United Nations (Okobukola, 2007)

Statement of the problem

Education, which has the potential for national transformation cannot be offered without adequate funding. Efforts so far made in this direction to the sector have been adjudged insufficient. This has resulted in the poor performance of graduates of Nigerian public tertiary institutions particularly those from the institutions under study. Inadequacy of funding creates challenges like in-conducive learning environment, ill-equipped school library, poor science laboratories, in attractive administrative office complexes, inadequacy lecture halls and theaters, among others which are found within the institutions. Intervention of Tertiary education Trust Fund in Nigeria has been able to make good provisions for easy educational facilitation particularly, some public universities, colleges of education, polytechnics and similar of such institutions but there is much room for improvement

Although, several studies have been done on educational funding, little is known to have comprehensively and adequately examined alternative sources of funding of various programmes and projects in public tertiary institutions and for educational sustainability in Nigeria, particularly in

Sokoto state. This study therefore, seeks to explore avenues that can be vigorously exploited in a bit to harness funding for tertiary educational development in the face challenging economic doldrums.

Research Questions

1. What are the effect of GDP on sources and applications of funds of public tertiary institutions in sokoto state?
2. To what extent could the infrastructure condition affect funding need that is supported by sources of finance of public tertiary institutions sokoto state?
3. To what extent could expenditure pattern and management governance agreed with financial regulations of public tertiary institutions in sokoto state?

Research Hypotheses

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the effect of GDP and sources and applications of funds of public tertiary institutions in sokoto state

Ho: There is no significant relationship between infrastructure condition and the support of funding needs and sources of finance of public tertiary institutions in sokoto state

Ho: There is no significant relationship between management governance and agreed expenditure pattern and financial regulations of public tertiary institutions in sokoto state

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the use of a cross-sectional survey approach designed as both disruptive and non-experiential as often used in developmental psychology, but also utilized in many areas including social sciences, management sciences and education. The study sought to examine an investigation into funding of tertiary institutions own by sokoto state under distressed economy among the generality of members of the society and thus the design of the study is mixed design approach to be in line with Taiwo, (2013) who observed that findings that, the challenges of implementing evidence-based and other innovative practices, treatments, interventions and programmes are sufficiently complex that a single methodological approach is often inadequate and that mixed method designs are preferable because they provide a better understanding of research issues than either qualitative or quantitative approaches alone. The former is important as it is used in interpreting and explaining result of the data while the latter quantifies the outcome of the variables (Kambari, 2017).The tertiary institutions in sokoto state, Nigeria was the population of the study which was made of up four (4} tertiary institutions of learning shehu shagari college of education sokoto, polytechnic of sokoto state, sokoto state university and College of Agriculture worno.These tertiary institutions of learning were selected using simple random sample. Based on Yamane formula of 1967 a sample of size of 171 was chosen as participants from four [4] tertiary institutions. For each of the four [4] sampled tertiary institutions research subjects were randomly selected in proportion of staff strength in the institutions. To enable the researcher elicited data from respondents, four rating scale structured questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was made up of the following options strongly agree;5-points;agree 4-points;neutral;3-points;disagree agree;3-points;strongly disagree;1-points.Expert from the tertiary institutions assessed the validity of instruments. The researcher administered 300 copies to respondents in the tertiary institutions in sokoto-Nigeria.

Reliability coefficient ranging from 0.70 to 0.73 was obtained. Secondary data were collected and used from four [4] tertiary institutions activities and achievement recorded to determine and evaluate the relationship between strategic managers, tactical, operational managers as well as staff of the tertiary institutions. The data was analyzed using standard deviation and regression analysis and data compiled from tertiary institutions to boost economic growth and development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Result and Discussions of Findings or answering research questions are presented in Table 1.1, 1.2, 1.3.

Research Question one: Sought to establish the extent Gross domestic product can affect sources and application of funds for tertiary institutions.**Resesrch Question two:** Sought to establish the extent that

infrastructure condition can affect funding needs on the sources and application supported for tertiary institutions.

Research Question three: Sought to establish the extent to which expenditure pattern and management governance can have an agreement with financial regulations of public tertiary institutions which was presented as: GDP, IC, and MGT.G respectively.

Table 1.Descriptive statistics core element of IFTIDECO

Variable	Mean	Median	Mode	Standard Deviation
GDP	4.25	4.00	4.00	0.752
IC	4.11	4.00	4.00	0.760
EP & MGT.G	4.18	4.00	4.00	0.729

Source: SPSS Version 20.0 Output

The table above is a summary of responses in respect of descriptive statistics of core elements on an investigation into funding of tertiary institutions own by sokoto state government. The table is in respect of measures of central tendency and standard deviation of data elicited by the study. The table shows the mean value and the standard deviation in respect of funding of tertiary institutions under distressed economy. (GDP) to be 4.25 and 0.752 respectively. This implies that the data in respect of GDP is mildly dispersed about the mean among the sampled organizations. The mode and the median for GDP is an indication that there is skewness in the distribution of data and is therefore almost symmetrical about the median, as an indication that tests of significance can be applied by either the use of normal distribution or t-distribution. The mean score and standard deviation in respect of effect infrastructure condition (IC) are 4.11 and 0.760 respectively. This suggests that the data in respect of IC is narrowly spread about the median and mode coinciding is an indication of normal distribution of data elicited for the study. Tests of significance can therefore be applied for IC by the use of z-score or t-score calculation at a suitable confidence level.

The table also indicates that for the data elicited in respect of key expenditure pattern and management governance (EP&MGT.G) the standard deviation of 0.729 is an indication of narrow spread about the mean of 4.18 and the agreement of the mode and the median at a value of 4.00 is an indication that there is no skewness in the distribution and the use of z-score or t-score for tests of significance at a desirable level of confidence in respect of impact of sound strategic policy-making and decisions is feasible. The agreement between the median and the mode at value of 4.00for all the core elements of funding of tertiary institutions under distressed economy implies that data elicited for the study meets the normal distribution requirement or the use of z-score or an approximation to it of t-score for tests of significance at a desired level of confidence.

The table also indicates that for the data elicited in respect of key strategic financial planning measures [EP&MGT.] the standard deviation of 0.729 is an indication of narrow spread about the mean of 4.18 and the agreement of the mode and the median at a value of 4.00 is an indication that there is no skewness in the distribution and the use of z-score or t-score for tests of significance at a desirable level of confidence in respect of expenditure pattern and management governance agreed with financial regulations of public tertiary institutions is feasible. The agreement between the median and the mode at value of 4.00for all the core elements of expenditure pattern and management governance implies that data elicited for the study meets the normal distribution requirement or the use of z-score or an approximation to it of t-score for tests of significance at a desired level of confidence

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

The table below presents the results of the tests for three (3) hypotheses of the study. The hypothesis linked the core elements of IFTIDECO under distressed economy as underlying construct as specified by an arrow. In testing the hypothesis, the standardized estimates relationship between variables of the core elements of the study under distressed economy represented by beta (β), the critical ratio (t-value) and

probability value (p-value) are obtained to represent relationship, decisions criteria and level of significance respectively

This is due to the fact that strength relationship between constructs is identified by β , and the strength of probability of results being acceptable is represented t-value and p-value (Maiyaki, 2018). As such, the tables from the SPSS output shows how these were used to test all the hypotheses of the study.

Table 2: Test of hypotheses

Hypothesized Path	Estimated β -Value	C.R (t-value)	p-Value
H ₁ : GDP \Rightarrow DECO	0.782	-25.181	0.000
H ₂ : IC \Rightarrow DECO	0.772	-24.282	0.000
H ₃ : EP&MGT.G \Rightarrow DECO	0.825	-29.645	0.000

Source: SPSS Version 20 Output

The acronyms for the hypotheses path in the table imply the following;

GDP: effect of gross domestic product [GDP] on sources and applications of funds of public tertiary institutions

IC: effect of infrastructure condition on the funding need that is supported by sources of finance of public tertiary institutions

EP&MGT.G: effect of expenditure pattern and management governance agreed with financial regulations of public tertiary institutions.

Hypothesis 1: Enunciated that there is no significant association between gross domestic product on sources and application of funds of public tertiary institutions under distressed economy in Sokoto-Nigeria. Results from the table refuted this assertion and therefore the alternative of strong assertion is accepted. The result shown in the hypothesized path for the behavior of GDP and DECO suggests statistical significance at 0.05 level of significance which translate to a positive association between GDP and DECO of the banking industry. The relationship is positive as evidenced by a regression coefficient (B) of 0.782 is strong and a t-value of -25.181 greater than a critical value of ± 1.96

Hypothesis 2: Enunciated that there is no significant relationship between infrastructure condition and support of funding needs and sources of finances in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto-Nigeria. From the SPSS output an alternative hypothesis is strongly accepted as statistically significance based on the statistic that, the p-value of 0.00 is below 0.05, the required level of significance and the t-value of -24.282 being greater than the critical threshold of ± 1.96 .The positive value of the regression β of coefficient 0.772. Indicates positive relationship between strategic financial management activities and business continuity and growth in the banking sub-sector in Sokoto-Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3 enunciated that there is no significant association between management governance and agreed pattern of expenditure in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto- Nigeria. Results from the table refuted this assertion and therefore the alternative of strong assertion is accepted. The result shown in the hypothesized path for the behavior of EP&MGT.G. and DECO suggests statistical significance at 0.05 level of significance at 95% confidence which translate to a positive association between EP&MGT.G.and DECO of the tertiary institutions.. The relationship is positive as evidenced by a regression coefficient (β) of 0.825 is strong and a t-value of -29.645 greater than a critical value of ± 1.96

CONCLUSIONS

In the last few decades, the educational sector in sokoto-State, has gone through radical changes and backwardness, prior to this period the educational sector was one of the prime driver of the Nigerian economy in those days few individuals, organizations, communities and society are engaged in

education, knowledge and skills acquisition with high quality and application in educational achievement as a means of providing jobs for the teeming population as well as generating revenue to support the economy, findings from the study has indicated that with funding of tertiary institutions in place in the educational sector, these could be a turnaround of the fortunes of education to the position of yester-years when sokoto-Nigeria was at the fore front in producing qualitative education with good management of resources and efficient and effective application to educational sector to generate revenue and fund education for enhancement of productivity in all sectors of the economy

RECOMMENDATIONS

The central challenge of global educational growth, development and sustainability often accomplished through competitiveness education, knowledge and skills suggests that educational policy-makers are often responsible for the fate of their educational affairs.

The study therefore make recommendations centered on re-thinking strategies especially liked to on an effective and efficient funding of tertiary institutions with a view to making education flourishing venture. To this end, the recommendations fare made based on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn therein.

- i) **Government and Policy-makers in education need** to realize the fact that no matter how small the sources are, is it is bound to make judicious application to tertiary institutions to bring positive change and thus have an impact under distressed economy and globalized world where the roles of nation states in poor management of resources are reduced. It therefore indicates that government at all level as a matter of necessity have enough skills and knowledge of education from the global perspective, acquire necessary skills for competing in the globalized educational sector and educational strategies from the global mindset because localized strategies are no longer effective for funding and sustainable in educational achievement
- ii) In addition to the sokoto government, some implications for practice emerged for other stakeholders, such as the national, international aid organizations, United Nations and corporate bodies. The external stakeholders may introduce training for the administrators on specific fiscal monitoring and evaluation practices which may permeate the tertiary institutions administration. Adoption of culture specific efficient and effective administrative practices may benefit the tertiary institutions in the state and federal level in Nigeria. In the long run, this may benefit the grant making by international aid organizations, as the administrators will already have prior know how on the administrative or audit practices..
- iii) Nigeria is a peculiar state and sokoto is part of it with a vast opportunities. This calls for educational policy-makers and the government search for and exploit new methods of financing education as an added advantage. Government are encouraged to exhibit global mindset by recognizing that education and business globalization favors companies that explore opportunities for enlarging their market-share in the world of business and make business more productive in an efficient manner. To succeed, educational policy-makers and the government are implored to make dramatic breakthroughs in improving the GDP, Inflation, Unemployment rate Exchange rate and management governance. Information explosion and technological advances are bringing world educational and businesses closely together thereby making services more over-crowded at an accelerating pace. Unless staff and students recognized the need for educational progress and development..
- iv) There is a distinctive role for government in improving the educational environment. This involves provision of an enabling environment for educational activities to flourish the government. Governments at all levels are urged to support the growth and development of education as the backbone of the national economy.
- v) Government of Nigeria especially Sokoto State is enjoined as a matter of urgency to objectively and realistically discuss the challenges confronting educational sector as a whole and escalating insecurity and banditry have conspired to effectively constrain educational institutions from playing

their role for fear of becoming victims of circumstances occasional by kidnapping and abductions. Such cries have a propensity to derail educational backward. for national progress, growth and development.

- vi) Educational policy-makers demand the pursuit of opportunities beyond controlled resources. Therefore instead of seeking for aid from banks for financial intervention for educational development and growth the government embark on massive mobilization of financial resources for investment is urged to in sector. This would aid in generating requisite capital infrastructure and technology inflows and related activities to boost education as knowledge in tertiary institutions

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was sponsored by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund through the Institution Based Research grant to Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto with grant number: TETF/DR & D/CE/COE/SOKOTO/IBR/2024/VOL.I/BATCH 10: S/NO.06

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